

“A Study To Assess The Knowledge Regarding Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder Among Mothers Of School Children In Nadathara Gramapanchayat, Thrissur”

Mrs. Ashmin Jolly¹, Ms. Angel E.V², Ms. Anngret K.V³, Mr. Mibin Babu⁴, M.s Nivya Johnson⁵,
Ms. Pooja Ramankutty⁶, Ms. Sanjana M.B⁷, Ms. Siya K.J⁸
Assistant Professor¹, 4th year B.SC Nursing students²⁻⁸
Aswini College Of Nursing¹⁻⁹

Abstract: Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder is a most commonly diagnosed childhood developmental disorder. It is characterized by persistent pattern of inattention, hyperactivity and impulsive behavior. Understanding the level of knowledge about ADHD among mothers is crucial for prompting a supportive and inclusive environment for those affected by the disorder. Considering this fact, a descriptive study was conducted to assess the level of knowledge regarding ADHD among mothers of school age children in selected Grama Panchayath Thrissur. The study also aimed to associate the level of knowledge regarding ADHD with their selected demographic variables. The samples were 60 mothers of school children, selected through convenient sampling technique, who fulfilled the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The data was collected using questionnaires regarding ADHD and demographic variables. The setting of the study was ward XII, XIII, XIV Nadathara Gramapanchayath, Thrissur. The collected data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The result showed that the majority 37(61.67%) had moderate knowledge, 12(20%) had adequate knowledge whereas 11(18.33%) had inadequate knowledge. Further analysis showed that there was significant association between the level of knowledge of mothers of school children regarding ADHD with their selected demographic variables such as age of mother (20.27), occupation of mother (14.58) and source of knowledge (44.77) while all other demographic variables showed no association. This study concluded that majority were having moderate knowledge. The study helped the mothers acquire knowledge of ADHD through the information booklet that was distributed among the subjects.

Key word: ADHD, school age children, knowledge, mother

INTRODUCTION

ADHD is the most common neurobehavioural disorder in childhood. It is characterized by inability to sustain concentration and may be accompanied by hyperactivity and impulsivity. Attention deficit can be conceptualized as a spectrum ranging from mild variations of normal to severe, chronic conditions. Studies suggest that approximately 4%-12% of school age children meet diagnostic criteria for the clinical disorder of ADHD.

Inattention, hyperactivity and impulsivity are the main characteristics of ADHD. Inattention refers to difficulty concentrating, forgetting instructions and moving from one task to another without completing anything. Impulsivity refers to talking over the top of others, having a 'short fuse',

and being accident-prone. Hyperactivity refers to constant restlessness and fidgeting. These children also experience academic underachievement, problems with interpersonal relationships with family members and peers, and low self-esteem.

NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The objective of the study was to determine the level of knowledge regarding Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder among mothers of school children. School children are developing and practicing skills and abilities that help them meet new people, get along with others and make new friends at school. They can pay attention for longer, might have more patience and might even be open to reasoning with others. But still they need help with expressing

emotions and behaving in positive ways, especially when they are tired or in a challenging social situations.

Children sometimes argue, are aggressive, or act angry or defiant around adults. A behaviour disorder may be diagnosed when these disruptive behaviours are uncommon for the child's age at the time, persist over time, or are severe. Disruptive behaviour disorders involve acting out and showing unwanted behaviour towards others.

Statement of the study

A study to assess the knowledge regarding Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder among mothers of school children at Nadathara Grama Panchayat, Thrissur.

Objectives of the study

- 1.To assess the level of knowledge regarding Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder among mothers of school children.
- 2.To associate the level of knowledge regarding Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder with their selected demographic variables.
- 3.To prepare and distribute information booklet regarding ADHD.

Hypothesis

H₁: There is a significant association between knowledge regarding ADHD among mothers of school age children with their selected demographic variables.

METHODOLOGY

Research Approach ; In this study Quantitative research approach was used

Methods of data collection

After getting permission from president of Nadathara Grama panchayath, Thrissur. The investigator explained the need and purpose of the study. Confidentiality of the information and privacy was assured. The time taken by the sample to complete the questionnaire was 20-30 minutes. After the collection of data the investigators distributed an information booklet to all mothers of school age children.

Research Design ;In this study Descriptive design was used

Demographic Variables-In this study the demographic variables are age of mother, age of

Copyright: Brio Innovative Journal of Novel Research (BIJNR)

child, gender of child , type of family, education qualification of mother, family monthly income , number of children, any complications during pregnancy, have you heard the about ADHD, source of information, and family history of ADHD.

In this study the population selected comprises of mothers of school aged children of ward XII, XIII and XIV of Nadathara Grama panchayath Target population ;All mothers of school age children

Accessible Population : The accessible population comprised of mothers of school age children who residing in ward XII, XIII and XIV at Nadathara, Thrissur.

Sampling Technique :The samples were collected through convenient sampling technique

Sample size :The sample of the present study comprised of 60 mothers of Nadathara Grama panchayath, Thrissur

Sample criteria Inclusion criteria

- willing to participate the study.
- able to read and write Malayalam.
- available during the study period
- live in Nadathara Gramapanchayath

Exclusion criteria:

- are not willing to participate in the study.
- cannot read and write malayalam.
- if the mother's have any problems like deaf, psychiatric illness.

Description and scoring

Section A: Description of demographic profile of mothers of school children

Section B: Description of the level of knowledge of mothers of school children regarding attention deficit hyperactivity disorder

Section C: Description of association between levels of knowledge of mothers about ADHD with their selected demographic variables.

RESULT FINDINGS:

SECTION A : Description on demographic profile of mothers of school children

Table 1 : Frequency and percentage distribution of the subjects according to the age of the mother, age of child, gender of child and educational qualification of mother.

Table (1)

SI NO	Demographic variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Age of the mothers (in years)		
	<20	0	0
	21-30	11	20
	31-40	46	75
	>40	3	5
2	Age of the child		
	6-8	23	35.55
	8-10	11	18.33
	10-12	26	43.34
3	Gender of the child		
	Male	34	56.67
	Female	26	43.33
	Others	0	0
4	Mother's education		
	Primary	7	11.66
	High school	10	16.67
	Higher secondary	19	31.67
	Diploma/Degree	12	20
	Post graduation	12	20

5.Regarding occupation of mother 26(43.34%) of mother are unemployed 15 (26.6%) mother are self employed 15 (25%) mother's are private employed and remaining 4 (6.66%) mother's had government job.

6•With regard to monthly income 22 (36.67%) had an income between \$5000-10000,18 (30%) had an income greater than \$20,000 13(21.67%) had an income between 10,000-20000 and remaining 7(11.66%) had an income less than \$5000.

7• With regard to type of family 35(58.34%) belongs to 9 nuclear family,23 (38.33%)belong to a joint family and remaining 2(3.33%) belong to extended family.

8•With regard to birth order majority of the sample 35(58.34%) have 2 child 14 (23.33%) have 1

child 6 (10%) have 3 child and 5(8.33%) have more than 3 child.

Section B: Description of the level of knowledge of mothers of school children regarding attention deficit hyperactivity disorder

Level of knowledge	Frequency	Percentage
Inadequate	11	18.33
Moderate	37	63.67
Adequate	12	20

DISCUSSION

Objective:1-To assess the knowledge regarding attention deficit hyperactivity disorder among mothers of school children

The current study revealed that among 60 subjects, 11(18.33%) had inadequate knowledge learning disability Whereas 37(61.67%) has moderate Knowledge and 12(20%) had adequate knowledge regarding attention deficit hyperactivity disorder .

Objective:2-To associate the level of knowledge regarding attention deficit hyperactivity disorder with their selected demographic variable

The present study revealed that there is a significant association between the knowledge among subject with selected demographic variables such as the age of mother ($\chi^2=20.27$), occupation of mother ($\chi^2=14.58$), and source of knowledge ($\chi^2=44.77$) .

Objective:3 To prepare and distribute information booklet regarding attention deficit hyperactivity disorder

An information booklet was prepared by investigator about ADHD it's types, etiology, clinical manifestations, diagnostic measures and management . It was validated by the experts in the subject . After assessing the knowledge,

information booklet was distributed to the sample in regional language.

Nursing implications

The findings of the study have several implications for nursing education, nursing practice, nursing administration and nursing research.

Limitations

- The study was conducted in a limited geographical area which may limit the generalization.
- Tool used for knowledge score were structured, thus free responses were restricted.
- Long term follow up was not possible because of limited availability of time.

Recommendations

On the basis of the study, recommendations have been made for future studies,

- A similar study can be carried out on large sample for longer period of time for broader generalization of result.
- A similar study can be conducted in different settings.
- A study can be conducted to evaluate efficacy of various teaching strategies like self instructional module, pamphlet, leaflets and computer assisted instructions on ADHD.
- A similar study can be replicated among mothers having children diagnosed with ADHD.

CONCLUSION : From this study it is clearly evident that majority of the mothers have moderate knowledge regarding Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder

REFERENCES

1. Kalia R. Textbook of Pediatric Nursing : South Asian Edition. Elsevier India; 2013.
2. Rimple Sharma. Essentials Of Pediatric Nursing. S.L.: Jaypee Brothers Medical P; 2020.
3. Judie A. Wong's Essentials of Pediatric Nursing: Second South Asian Edition. Elsevier India; 2018.
4. Panchali pal. Textbook of pediatric nursing for BSc nursing students. 1st edition . New Delhi. India.

5.Problems in children [Internet].
Physiopedia. Available from:
[https://www.physiopedia.com/Behavioral problems in children](https://www.physiopedia.com/Behavioral_problems_in_children)